

Studies on the role of Pantothenate in Streptococcal Growth at Different Temperatures

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The effect of environmental pantothenate levels on the growth of *Streptococcus faecalis* ATCC 9790 was studied in terms of growth and lysis rates and depletion phenomena at 38° and 45°. Low levels of pantothenate at both the temperatures yielded normal exponential cells upto peak turbidities which were functions of pantothenate concentrations. Attainment of the peaks at both the temperatures were followed by prompt lysis. At 45° the growth peaks were significantly lower than at 38°. The lysis obtained at both the temperatures were insensitive to chloramphenicol. Additional experiments with low pantothenate grown cells indicated sensitiveness of these cells to both penicillin and chloramphenicol indicating that wall and protein synthesis were still operative in these types of pantothenate deficient cells.

PANTOTHENIC acid is an essential growth factor for *Streptococcus faecalis* and is also an essential building block of the two acyl transfer factors, e.g. CoA and ACP. Synthesis of N-acetyl hexosamines which are cell wall building blocks, and the synthesis of lipids which are membrane building blocks, both involve acyl transport^{1, 2}. Toennies *et al.*¹ suggested that in fermentative organisms pantothenate action might be confined to wall and membrane synthesis, and that these two processes differ in their quantitative dependence on pantothenate.

Damage or loss of integrity of integumental structures—cell wall and membrane has been reported to be the primary events^{3, 4, 5} in bacteria when incubation temperature is raised above the optimum with subsequent development of lytic tendency as a result of this. Toennies *et al.*¹ reported that during growth (38°) in low pantothenate level *S. faecalis* developed deficiency in membrane synthesis to a greater degree than the wall synthesis. It appeared from these observations that the synthesis of these two integumental structures would likely to be more affected if such cells are grown at some temperature higher than the optimum and on low pantothenate levels. To test this, comparative studies on the effects of incubation temperatures, i.e. 38° and 45° upon the growth and lysis of *Streptococcus faecalis* grown with different pantothenate levels were undertaken.

Experimental

Bacterial strain, media, growth conditions and measurements :

Streptococcus faecalis ATCC 9790 was grown (in calibrated culture tubes 19×150 mm with Morton stainless steel closures) in a synthetic non-limited

complete medium* buffered at pH 6.5 with 0.3 M phosphate⁶, and the basal medium was sterilized by passing it through a 0.45 μ Millipore metal filter. Growth of cultures was measured by determining directly turbidity of the culture tubes in a colorimeter (Photochem. Colorimeter C-110, red filter, with test tube holder for insertion of the culture tubes) at an interval of about 20 min. Optical densities were adjusted to AOD (adjusted optical density) values which are proportional to bacterial concentrations⁷.

The inoculum was grown (38°) in 6 ml. of finished non-limited complete medium with 400 μ g calcium pantothenate per ml. From an initial bacterial concentration of AOD about 2, an inoculum culture of AOD 240, consisting of active cells in early log phase was grown in about 3 hr and chilled. The cells were spun down (5°) and supernatant was rejected. The pellet was once washed with same volume of sterile water and finally re-suspended in the same volume of ice-cold sterile distilled water. This suspension was used for inoculating the experimental tubes at the rate of 1 drop per 6 ml of finished medium. Haake stirrer-water bath was used for incubation. Penicillin (Penicillin G, 50 μ g per ml of finished medium) and chloramphenicol (210 μ g per ml. of finished medium) solutions used were sterilized by passing them through membrane filter.

Results and Discussion

Figures 1 and 2 show characteristic data. It will be evident from these that the peak growth at both the temperatures was evident on environmental pantothenate level. Termination of growth in both

* dl-phenylalanine, dl-methionine, dl-tryptophane and dl-tyrosine were used instead of the corresponding l-amino acids as they were not available.

the cases was followed by prompt lysis and there was no evidence of any post-exponential growth.

It is further apparent (Figs. 1 and 2) that the duplication rate (at relatively higher pantothenate levels when the rates at both temperatures tended to be constant) at 38° showed to be slightly faster than at 45°. With decreasing pantothenate levels, however, the duplication rate tended to decrease, while the net rate of lysis tended to increase more faster at 45° than at 38°. The reasons why growth rates are slower under substrate restriction are probably complex and are only vaguely conceived. The inability of transport systems to promote accumulation of the limiting substrate is probably an important part of the whole story⁸ but perhaps not all.

A comparative study of the data in Table 1 compiled from Figs. 1 and 2 will revealed that for all levels of pantothenate in the medium growth peaks were significantly higher at 38° than those at 45°.

Fig. 1. Growth of *Streptococcus faecalis* on low pantothenate concentrations. The tubes were inoculated with a calculated OD of 2 and incubated at 38°, AOD readings being taken periodically. The curves represent from left to right, the responses to 0, 5, 10, 20, 50 µg of calcium pantothenate per ml. The cultures were run simultaneously but for clarity the curves have been separated by some spaces on the time scale. The minutes shown on the ascending and descending branches show approximate duplication times and half-times of lysis, respectively.

Incubation at 38°

Fig. 2. Growth of *Streptococcus faecalis* on low pantothenate concentrations. The tubes were incubated at 45°. The other conditions were same as stated under Fig. 1.

TABLE 1. GROWTH PEAKS OF *Streptococcus faecalis* ATCC 9790 GROWING EXPONENTIALLY AT 38° AND 45° IN THE PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT LEVELS OF EXOGENOUS PANTOTHENATE IN THE MEDIUM

Millimicrogram of pantothenate per ml. of medium	0	5	10	20	50
Growth peaks (AOD) 38°	15	54	240	580	1140
45°	5	8	60	370	800
Growth Peaks at 45° expressed as percentage of growth peaks at 38°	34	15	25	64	70

It will be further evident (Table 1) that at higher temperature the growths of the cells grown with low pantothenate were more affected than those grown with relatively higher levels of pantothenate. Hoffman *et al.*³ also reported higher incubation temperature (45°) to cause cell wall damage (increase of lysozyme sensitivity) in *E. coli* unlike at 38°. Damage of cytoplasmic membrane and subsequent lysis following increase of temperature over the optimum has also been reported recently by Morita⁵.

Although the results of additional experiments (Fig. 3) supports the view that even in low pantothenate grown cells cell-wall (peptidoglycan) synthesis (as indicated from the proneness of such cells to

addition of penicillin in the exponential phase, Fig. 3) and protein synthesis (as indicated from the termination of exponential growth and initiation of postexponential protracted growth following addition of chloramphenicol in the exponential phase) were still operative, alteration of the rates of these two macromolecular synthesis due to curtailment of membrane synthesis¹ cannot however be precluded.

The thermal effects of raising the incubation temperature from 38° to 45° could simply intensify the damaging actions discussed in the preceding paragraph, causing lowered net utilization of pantothenate within the cell and thereby explaining the obtention (Table 1) of lower peak growths at 45° than at 38°. This would imply higher requirements of pantothenate for cells when they are grown at a temperature higher than the optimum. As a matter of fact

needed for the synthesis of the integumental structures. Had it been the otherwise one could have expected no promotion of growth at 45° with increasing pantothenate levels unlike reported here (Table 1).

It is of interest to note (Figs. 1 and 2) that the termination of growth at both the temperatures was followed by prompt lysis. Two questions arise. Was the observed lysis an active process? Why there was lysis at all? Addition of chloramphenicol (Fig. 3) at the peak showed to have no significant influence upon the rate of lysis. This indicated that the lysis observed was not an active process and did not require the synthesis of proteins (although protein synthesis was possible in the medium used) as reported by Henning *et al.*¹⁰. These workers reported that the lysis of an oleate-auxotroph of *E. coli* K-12 on starvation of oleate (one class of building blocks for cell envelopes) during growth in

Fig. 3. Effect of penicillin and chloramphenicol upon *Streptococcus faecalis* grown (38°) on 20 μg of calcium pantothenate per ml. The arrows indicate the addition of the antibiotics. Symbols: \circ , represents growth curve of the control; \bullet , represents growth curve after addition of penicillin; \triangle , represents growth curve after addition of chloramphenicol.

changes of cellular composition and increase in nutrients requirements following elevation of growth temperature have already been reported in the literature⁹.

It seems further (Table 1) that the raising of temperature from 38° to 45° did cause some, if any, but not complete damage of the enzyme systems of the cells involved in the acyl transport factors

nutrient broth was dependent on the synthesis of proteins (chloramphenicol prevented this lysis). Addition of penicillin at peak growth (Fig. 3) also had no significant effect upon the rate of lysis indicating presumably that wall synthesis was not occurring after the attainment of peak turbidity.

Generally depletion of nutrients which are structural components of cell wall leads to lysis whereas

depletion of other nutrients is followed by post-exponential synthesis of cell wall and membrane^{11,12}. Accordingly on depletion of pantothenate from the medium the cofactors (CoA and ACP) derived from pantothenate which were in turnover and suffered net degradation during the exponential growth phase and did not seem capable of production of acyl compounds needed for synthesis of the integumental structures. Recently Das and Toennies¹³ reported that cellular CoA is degraded during balanced growth and is replaced at the rate of approximately 20% per division period during growth in abundance of pantothenate. They also observed significant reduction in the contents of CoA and ACP per cell during exponential growth of *S. faecalis* in low pantothenate medium. Reduction of total cellular lipid synthesis in pantothenate deficiency has been reported¹⁴. Henning *et al.*¹⁰ observed inhibition of DNA, RNA, protein, and phospholipid syntheses, death and lysis following oleate starvation in an oleate auxotroph of *E. coli* K-12. Whether pantothenate dependent lysis could cause similar phenomena remains to be seen.

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